

THE EFFECTS OF VISCOELASTICITY ON THE FATIGUE PERFORMANCE OF FOAM CORE SANDWICH STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT: Sandwich structures used in many modern day applications essentially consist of two stiff face sheets and a viscoelastic foam core. These cores are generally more sensitive to the testing environment than their metal or ceramic counterparts and their fatigue life is controlled by factors such as frequency and temperature. These factors are of considerable interest and practicality for the safe design of foam core sandwich structures. In order to investigate the effects of frequency, flexural fatigue tests were performed on sandwich beams with core densities of 130 and 260 kg/m³ at frequencies of 3 and 15Hz. S-N diagrams were generated and it was observed that the fatigue strength decreased with increased stress and increased with core density, and the number of cycles to failure, N_f , increased with increase in frequency. In all cases failure was dominated by a primary shear crack in the core however the crack path varied with frequency. In order to investigate the effects of temperature, two types of PVC cores of the same nominal density were used to manufacture the sandwich panels; one was linear HD foam and the other, a slightly cross-linked H foam. Fatigue tests were conducted on these structures at room temperature (RT), 40° and 80°C. The tests were conducted on an MTS machine equipped with an environmental chamber. S-N diagrams revealed that fatigue life decreased with increased temperatures. At RT, HD structures revealed much longer fatigue life compared to H structures however at elevated temperatures, a complete reversal of this trend was seen. Failure in both HD and H constructions occurs in the core. For H130 beams, at room temperature and 40°C, brittle fracture occurs beyond the elastic range and plastic yielding at 80°C. For HD structures however, at RT, brittle failure occurs after the elastic-plastic range and plastic yielding at elevated temperatures. Details of the experimentation, the analysis of the fatigue data, and damage mechanisms are presented.

INTRODUCTION

Sandwich structures are used in many applications mainly because the concept is very suitable for lightweight structures with high in plane and flexural stiffness. The face sheets carry most of the bending and in-plane loads while the core provides the flexural stiffness and the out-of-plane shear and compressive strength [1]. In applications such as ship structures, closed-cell viscoelastic PVC foam cores are used. The low weight of the foam core gives good buoyancy and low displacement of the hull and the relative ease in producing large sandwich components; makes them attractive for such structures [2]. In these applications the structure is subjected changes in temperature and frequency. While many works on the effects of temperature and frequency on composite laminates [3-6] and resin systems [7-8] may be found in the open literature there is little or no quantitative research on the effects of temperature and frequency on foam core sandwich structures. It is well known that a polymer can be in different regimes or states depending mainly on the surrounding temperature and partly on the molecular properties [9]. Amorphous and semi crystalline polymers do not have a distinct melting point, but a glass transition temperature; T_g . Polymers generally have glass temperature above room temperature. Dramatic changes in the characteristics of a number of properties of the polymer occur around this temperature. Below the glass transition temperature, amorphous polymer is in a glassy regime, where the elastic modulus is a direct reflection of the stiffness of the intermolecular bonds, which is the so-called Van-der-Waals bond. These bonds hold the molecules together. Since these bonds are not as strong as covalent bonds that normally exist between carbon atoms, they will deflect when a polymer is loaded. The Van-der-Waals bonds are easily influenced by temperature causing the stiffness to decrease with increase in temperature [10]. Such complex behavior under elevated temperatures will most certainly affect the performance of structural PVC foams used here as a core material. The constant battering of waves further exacerbates the problem. It is well known that during each loading cycle, we get a hysteresis loop, the area of which represents the energy spent in the cycle. Most of the hysteretic energy is dissipated as heat, and if the material is not a good thermal conductor, as is the case for PVC foam cores [11], then a temperature rise may occur. Pandita et al [12] studied tension-tension behavior of woven fabric composites at different frequencies and found that at a frequency of 5Hz hysteresis heating occurs. Such hysteretic heating and the resultant thermal softening may drastically affect the fatigue performance of the material. The degree of thermal softening during fatigue will depend on the magnitude and frequency of the applied stress and on the viscoelastic characteristics of the material, hence the focus in this study shall be on the viscoelastic core and not on the face sheets since little or no frequency effects is found when the fiber /matrix bonding is strong [13]. The heterogeneous material response under elevated temperatures and fluctuating frequencies is unknown and hence there is often a tendency to 'over design' sandwich structures mainly because of uncertainties about their performance. Conservative design practices result in heavier and more costly components. The objective of this work therefore is to assess the durability of, and to establish damage mechanisms in sandwich structures subjected various frequencies and temperatures.

EXPERIMENTAL

In this study S2 glass fiber/vinylester sandwich constructions with closed cell PVC foam cores were used. Six layers of plain weave S2-glass fiber preforms with the 0/90° orientation were placed on an aluminum tool. PVC foam core was then placed between the stacked preforms. (R75, H130, HD130, R260, and R300 were used. All the cores employed were slightly cross-linked with the exception of the HD cores, which are linear. After stacking, a resin infusion and suction line was installed and the entire assembly was vacuum bagged. The system was debulked for several hours prior to resin infusion. Vinylester (Dow Derakane 411-350) resin manufactured by Dow Corning was used. Vacuum was kept on until the complete cure took place. The thickness of the face sheets was 3.8 mm, while that of core was 12.7 mm.

STATIC TEST

Static tests were conducted on R75, H130, HD130, R260, and R300 at room temperature in displacement control at a crosshead speed of 1.27 mm/min. Additionally static tests were conducted on H130 and HD130 at 40° and at 80°C. Tests at elevated temperatures were conducted in an environmental chamber fitted onto a servo hydraulic testing machine (MTS) with 100kN load capacity. The temperature in the environmental chamber was controlled with a model 779 MTS electronic controller.

Figure 1 Three-point bend test conducted within an environmental test chamber

Sandwich beams of dimensions 16.5mm x 16.5mm x 200mm were cut from the manufactured panels for quasi-static and fatigue tests using a Felker saw fitted with a diamond coated steel blade. The beams were tested in three-point bend configuration with a span length of 160mm. A loading nose with a radius of 10mm was used in order to prevent localized indentations in the face sheet of the beams. For sandwich beams the stress, F , in the face sheets is [14];

$$F = \frac{P L}{2 t_f (t_s + t_c) b} \quad (1)$$

where P is the applied load, L is the span length, t_f is the thickness of the face sheet, t_s is the thickness of the sandwich, t_c is the thickness of the core and b is the width of the beam. The stress in the beam is equivalent to the facing stress.

A minimum of four replicate specimens of each sandwich type was prepared for the static tests. Heating rates were kept to 10°C/min to minimize any thermal shock effects. After reaching the target temperature the chamber temperature was kept constant for at least 1 hour before the start of testing to allow for thermal equilibrium. In order to monitor the temperature of the beams an Omega HH12 digital thermometer with two external probes was used. One probe was attached onto the side of the core and the other probe was used to measure the surrounding air inside the chamber. Ideally, insertion of the temperature probe into the core would yield accurate core temperature but may cause a high stress zone and consequently accelerate failure. Therefore the probe was glued to the side of the beam and covered with a piece of foam for insulation. At all times the air temperature inside the chamber was accurate to within 2°C of the values displayed on the electronic controller. Once the beams reached the required temperature they were tested in displacement control at a crosshead speed of 1.27 mm/min.

CYCLIC FLEXURE

Cyclic flexural tests were performed on a minimum of four replicate sandwich beams of the same dimensions as in static tests as per ASTM C393-62 [15]. The tests were performed on H130, HD130 and R260 beams at room temperature and thereafter on H130 and HD130 at 40 and 80°C, under load control at a stress ratio, $R = |P_{\min}| / |P_{\max}| = 0.1$, using the MTS machine described earlier. The beams were cycled at frequencies of 3 and 15 Hz. At elevated temperatures the frequency was set at 3 Hz. Fatigue data were generated at stress levels of: 90%, 85%, 80% and 75% of the static ultimate flexural strength. The fatigue life of the specimens is characterized as the number of cycles to ultimate failure. The applied maximum bending stress is plotted against the number of cycles on a log-log scale.

POST FRACTURE EXAMINATION

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM, JSM 5800 JEOL) was used to examine the morphologies of fractured surfaces and to investigate the influence of frequency and temperature on the formation of micro-cracks within the specimens. Additionally, the failed beams were examined in a Unitron optical microscope model FSB coupled to a complete video image marker system VIA150.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Quasi Static

Representative load-deflection curves for four types of sandwich beams (performed at room temperature) are shown in Figure 2. It was observed that the sandwich structures with low core densities, viz: R75 and H130, exhibit ductile behavior while the sandwich structures with high core densities viz: R260 and R300, exhibit brittle type characteristics.

Figure 2 Load–displacement curves for sandwich beams (tests performed at rt).

As expected the stiffness and failure load of the sandwich beams increased with increase in core density. This trend was reminiscent to trend seen in a previous study conducted on the foams without face sheets [15]. Failure occurred at small deflections of the beam and was characterized by failure in the core. In some instances localized “stress whitening” and wrinkling of the GFRP face sheet occurred at or near the point of loading. This was immediately followed by compaction and crushing of the core, which marked the final failure event.

Figures 3(a-b) show representative load-displacement curves (at three temperatures) for HD and H sandwich beams respectively. The mechanical properties such as flexural modulus and strength decreased with increased temperature however the decrease was more substantial in the HD beams. Close inspection of the beams revealed that damage mainly occurred in the cores and was more severe in the HD beams. This suggests that linear foam cores are more temperature sensitive than cross-linked foam cores. The temperature sensitivity was indicated by the extent of the damage in the core.

Figure 3 Load-displacement curves at RT, 40 and 80°C for (a) HD and (b) H sandwich structures.

HD beams tested at RT revealed a linear load–displacement ($P-\delta$) response as shown in Figure 3(a). After reaching approximately 70% of the ultimate load the response became non-linear and the material exhibited ductile behavior. This non-

linearity continued up until the maximum load was reached. Thereafter yielding occurred in the core and this corresponded with compaction of foam cells just below the tougher resin rich interface. Further compaction and crushing of the core marked the final failure event. Test data at 40°C revealed a significant reduction in the mechanical properties. The maximum load to failure and stiffness was found to reduce by approximately 60% and 75% respectively. The reduction in stiffness resulted in increased deflection of the beam at correspondingly lower loads. At 80°C further degradation of the core was observed and was accompanied by a dramatic loss in stiffness, which is indicated by the non-linear load-displacement (P-δ) response. After taking up a small initial load (less than 10% of the load at RT) plastic yielding occurred the core. The beam remained plastically strained after the removal of the load and is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4 Plastically strained H130 beam after quasi-static test at 80°C

H130 like the HD130 beams demonstrated linear load response at room temperature; however they carried marginally lower loads and exhibited brittle failure. The principal mode of failure was core shear. In some instances stress whitening or crazing was evident on the face sheets. At 40°C, the stiffness of the beams decreased marginally and a somewhat similar load response was observed, hence the linear portion of the graph superposed the RT curve. This suggests that H130 beams with cross-linked foam cores are relatively less dependent on temperature, at least in this temperature range. Failure at 40°C was similar to that at RT and was characterized by core shear. At 80°C however, plastic yielding occurred in the core and the beams failed by collapse and compaction of foam cells at relatively low loads. Accordingly, failure in HD and H constructions, which occurred mainly in the core, may be summarized as follows; For H130 beams brittle fracture occurred beyond the elastic range at room temperature and at 40°C and plastic yielding at 80°C. For HD structures however, brittle failure occurred after the elastic-plastic range at RT and plastic yielding at the elevated temperatures. Although the properties of both cross-linked and linear foams are dependant on the temperature, the differences in the failure mechanisms suggest that cross-linked cores give PVC mechanical stability at elevated temperatures.

FLEXURAL FATIGUE RESULTS

Flexural fatigue tests were performed on H130 and R260 beams, at rt and at 3 and 15Hz. The variation of the fatigue strength as a function of the stress level is presented in the form of S-N diagrams in Figures 5(a-b). During the tests no visible changes were observed on specimen for most of its fatigue life, although an increase in the temperature of the core was recorded. Beams cycled at 3 Hz measured a temperature increase of $2\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$, while those cycled at 15 Hz measured a temperature increase of $12\pm 2^\circ\text{C}$. Shortly before failure numerous small shear cracks formed in the core. They coalesced into a larger more dominant crack that propagated from the compression side to the tension side of the beam, details of which are given later. Shear yielding occurred in the core during the final stages. At this time substantial stiffness degradation occurred, causing a rapid increase in the deflection of the central portion of the beam and the subsequent failure.

Figure 5 Log-Log Representation of S-N data for Sandwich Beams tested at 3 and 15 Hz. R=0.1. a) H130 b) R260.

The characteristics of the S-N curves are typical for structural material where fatigue strength decreases with increased stress. The lower density H130 sandwich beams have lower fatigue strength than R260 beams as indicated. Since the face sheets of

H130 and R260 beams were made of the same material, we conclude that the fatigue strength increases with increased foam density. Figures 5(a-b) also shows that fatigue life increased with the increase in frequency and the data fit a straight line on a log-log plot. Unlike other structural materials such as steels, there is no indication of an endurance limit, at least not within the range of cycles considered herein.

Number of cycles to failure as a function of the frequency

The number of cycles to failure, N_f at 3 and 15 Hz decreased as fatigue stress increased and the difference in N_f at 3 and 15 Hz for each set of beams decreased as the stress levels increased. N_f at 15Hz was at least two times greater than N_f at 3 Hz for both sets of beams. In general the number of cycles to failure at 15 Hz was greater than the number of cycles to failure at 3 Hz, $N_{f(15Hz)} > N_{f(3Hz)}$. One possible explanation for increase in no of cycles to failure at 15 Hz may be derived from the concept; 'Work Energy = frictional energy + strain energy'. Work or input energy at any given stress level at both 3 and 15 Hz is constant. The temperature measured in the core of the beams tested at 15 Hz was $12 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$. This means that frictional energy was converted into heat energy leaving less available strain energy to fuel the damage process. Hence beams tested at 15 Hz survived at greater number of cycles before failure.

FLEXURAL FATIGUE AT ELEVATED TEMPERATURES

Here the results of fatigue tests at three different temperatures, the macroscopic behavior trends in stiffness, and the post mortem microscopic evaluation of damage mechanisms in HD and H sandwich beams are given. Fatigue tests are analyzed in the S-N diagrams shown in Figures 6(a-b). For both types of beams the number of cycles to failure at RT was considerably higher than at the elevated temperatures and the fatigue life increased with decreased stress and decreased with increased temperature.

Figures 6 S-N curves at RT, 40 and 80°C for (a) HD sandwich beams and (b) H sandwich beams.

The number of cycles to failure, N_f for HD beams was significantly higher than that for H beams at RT, however at elevated temperatures the reverse was true. Figure 6a reveals that the fatigue life of HD beams decreases substantially at elevated temperatures, particularly at 80°C. At this temperature the beams failed after 10^4 fatigue cycles while they sustained 10^6 cycles when tested at RT, both these tests being done at a stress level of 60%. This equates to a 99 % reduction in fatigue life. H130 beams on the other hand were not as temperature sensitive. Figure 6(b) shows that the fatigue data trends at 40°C and at RT are fairly similar, however at 80°C premature failure occurs. This was due to substantial degradation in the core.

FAILURE ANALYSIS

H130 and R260 beams tested at 3 and 15Hz.

Failure in the H130 and R260 beams tested at 3 and 15 Hz occurred in the core. The crack paths in H130 and R260 beams subjected to cyclic loading at 3 and 15 Hz are shown in Figures 7(a-b). The crack path in the core of the H130 sandwich at 3Hz was distinctly different from that at 15Hz, however the crack path in the core of R260 beams was similar at both frequencies.

Figure 7 Fatigue crack path through the core at room temperature and at 90% of ultimate load, $R=0.1$ (a) H130 (b) R260

As stated previously, numerous minute cracks initiated in the core, just below the point of loading. The cracks grew together forming a single dominant crack that propagated on the compression side of the beam, just below the resin rich interface, parallel to beam until they reached some critical length. For H130, this critical length at 3 Hz was substantially longer than at 15 Hz, this being the only difference that was observed. After reaching this critical length, the crack kinked at an angle of approximately of 45° toward the tension side of the beam. It then propagated in the core on the tension side delaminating toward the edge of the beam. One possible reason for the difference in crack paths in the H130 may be due to localized heating in the central portion of the core. The higher core temperature at 15Hz makes the core more compliant and hence delays crack propagation. In order to verify this theory, a fresh set of beams was cooled, by blowing air over the beams, while they were cycled at a frequency of 15 Hz. The ensuing crack resembled the crack seen at 3 Hz. Crack path in the core of the R260 sandwich beams at both frequencies was similar to crack path of H130 beams tested 3Hz. R260 cores are more dense and less affected by heat, hence no difference in the crack paths at 3 and 15 Hz was observed.

HD130 at room temperature

HD beams subjected to cyclic loading at RT demonstrated a remarkable resistance to crack initiation and no damage was visible for at least 80% of the fatigue life. Soon thereafter a narrow band of collapsed cells of the order of one cell size (0.3-0.4mm) appeared in the core just below the interface on the compression side of the beam. The band of collapsed cells increased in length to approximately 40mm before a second tier of collapsed cells appeared immediately below the first. These bands of collapsed cells progressed toward the tension side of the beam, leading to a loss in stiffness and subsequent increase in the deflection of the central part the beam. Failure of the face sheets ensued. Matrix cracking and fiber breakage was the principal mode of failure in the face sheets. Figure 8(a) shows bands of collapsed cells through the thickness of sandwich structure and Figure 8(b) shows failure of the upper face sheet.

Figure 8 (a) Bands of collapsed of cells in HD core after 10^6 fatigue cycles at RT. $P=0.65P_{ult}$, $R=0.1$, $f=3\text{Hz}$, 8(b) Matrix cracking, fiber breakage and delamination on the upper face sheet of HD sandwich after 10^6 cycles at RT. $R=0.1$, $f=3\text{Hz}$.

H130 and HD130 tested at Elevated Temperatures

At 40°C a fair amount of degradation occurred in the core of the HD beams and collapsed cells were clearly visible close to the upper and lower face sheets. These collapsed cells led to a reduction in height of the beams and hence a volume change. Correspondingly, deflection in the central part of the beam increased leading to failure. No cracks were evident in the core of these beams at this temperature. At 80°C a similar damage mechanism was seen initially, however this time a substantially larger volume change occurred. The volume change was due in part to a reduction in height of the core. The core also concaved as shown in Figure 9 and once again no cracks were evident in the core. Core collapse was the main mode of failure at elevated temperatures.

Figure 9 Degradation of HD core after 5×10^3 cycles at 80°C . The core concaved and the height of the beam reduced.

Additionally, the matrix resin decomposed at 80°C and there was a strong odor of resin. HD foams do not lead the heat away easily and hence the resin in the interface area decomposed and this resulted in face/core delamination at the edges as shown in Figure 10(a). Delamination also occurred at the point of loading as shown in Figure 10(b).

Figure 10(a-b) HD sandwich beams after 10^6 cycles at 80°C (a) face /core delamination (b) delamination of face sheets at point of loading.

At this time the load carried by the matrix decreased and was shed to the fibers. This led to an increase in the strain in the essentially elastic fibers. As the stresses in the fibers increased they began to break randomly leading to the final failure event.

H130 beams tested at 40°C displayed a similar damaged mechanism except for a minor amount of compaction in the core prior to the final failure event. At 80°C however, failure was by gradual compaction of the core. Sandwich structures tested herein have closed cell PVC cores. These cores have a very low thermal conductivity. Typically conductivity values range from 0.12-0.18 W/mK. These low thermal conductivity values mean that these cores are good insulators, but a consequence of that is that the material has limited ability to lead away heat. As seen in this study even a small increase in temperature causes a drastic reduction in fatigue life especially with linear HD cores.

CONCLUSIONS

The effects of frequency and temperature on the fatigue behavior of foam core sandwich composites have been investigated and the following conclusions have been drawn from this study.

- 1) The stiffness and failure load of the sandwich beams increased with increased core density and decreased with increased core temperature.
- 2) The number of cycles to failure, N_f , for H130 and R260 beams, increased with the increase in frequency.
- 3) A significant increase in core temperature was measured in H130 beams cycled at 15 Hz. At a frequency of 3 Hz core temperature was $2 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ and at a frequency of 15 Hz core temperature was $12 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$. This increase in core temperature made the cores more compliant and this in turn altered crack propagation path. Fatigue crack path in the core of the H130 sandwich beams differed significantly when tested at loading frequencies of 3 and 15 Hz. The difference in the crack paths in the H130 cores is attributed to heating in the core.
- 4) Failure in both HD and H constructions occurs in the PVC core. For H130 beams, at room temperature and 40°C , brittle fracture occurs beyond the elastic range and plastic yielding at 80°C . For HD structures however, at RT, brittle failure occurs after the elastic-plastic range and plastic yielding at elevated temperatures.
- 5) The behavior of PVC foams is influenced by the presence of cross-links. HD cores have no cross-links and hence degraded faster than H130 foams at elevated temperatures.
- 6) The fatigue life increased with core density and decreased stress and decreased with increased temperatures. At RT the fatigue life of HD beams was significantly longer than H beams; however at elevated temperatures the reverse was true.
- 7) HD cores displayed an extraordinary ability in avoiding crack initiation and this resulted in the beams sustaining considerably higher number of cycles prior to failure at RT. At elevated temperatures however, HD beams collapsed much faster than the H beams and the strength reduced almost catastrophically.

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